

Big data platform and identification of prediction models using temporal data acquired in other RM for resource optimization

SPOKE N 6 Primary Agroindustry

Flagship project FORMIDABILÆ-RM5

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Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, and demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Platform description

1.1. Platform architecture description

The Big Data Platform is based on a modular, containerized architecture and is based on S3-compatible object storage, enabling management of the entire data lifecycle (ranging from orchestration to ingestion, analytics, and self-service use with advanced reporting and visualizations).

The following components, mentioned below, enable comprehensive management of the data lifecycle.

Apache Airflow enables both batch (data warehousing, historical analysis) and streaming (critical events in real time) modes which coexist synergistically, supported by self-service sandboxes that allow data scientists and analysts to run Jupyter notebooks, import libraries, and train ML models directly on enterprise data.

Data ingestion is managed by Apache NiFi, delivered as a containerized service on Kubernetes, which uses over 300 processors for routing, transformation, and format conversion (CSV, JSON, XML, Avro), tracks every event with its data provenance engine, automatically adjusts backpressure, and leverages parameterized templates to version and reuse complex pipelines.

Above the storage and compute layer, Hue and Superset, also containerized on Kubernetes and integrated with Keycloak/OpenLDAP SSO and Apache Ranger governance, offer users differentiated self-service experiences:

Hue provides a file manager for Ozone, an advanced SQL Editor for Hive and Trino with autocompletion and saving results, dashboards and interactive documents that combine SQL blocks, graphs, and text.

Superset, for its part, serves as a drag-and-drop BI engine for advanced reports and visualizations (bar charts, lines, pivot tables, maps), supports scheduling reports via email or webhooks and setting alerts based on KPI thresholds, and is extendable via Python plugins for new chart types and additional connectors.

The IoT platform, built on ThingsBoard, offers a robust and flexible foundation for managing devices and data across a wide range of Internet of Things scenarios. Thanks to a modular microservices architecture and use of container technology, the platform can scale horizontally and maintain high availability even in case of node failures. Scalability and fault tolerance are assured by the fact that each node in a ThingsBoard cluster is identical and independent, which means there's no master node and the platform can replace failed nodes automatically, avoiding downtime and loss of data. Device connectivity is highly versatile: the platform supports industry-standard protocols such as MQTT, CoAP and HTTP, and accommodates both modern and legacy devices. Secure onboarding and provisioning processes ensure that each device is authenticated and managed safely within the system.

All incoming telemetry and event data can be collected in real time and stored in scalable solutions such as NoSQL (for example Cassandra) or relational databases like PostgreSQL. The rule engine, accessed through a visual editor, makes it easy to set up complex data processing workflows. This flexibility allows transformation, enrichment, and filtering of incoming messages, as well as the triggering of conditional logic for events and alarms. Users can define their own workflows for event detection, notification, and automated actions, covering scenarios as diverse as device failures, threshold breaches or custom business rules, supporting proactive and automated monitoring and response.

Remote device management is enabled using secure, programmable RPC commands. Rules and alarms can be configured to cascade across device groups, assets, or organizational hierarchies. The platform supports real-time monitoring, where alarms and notifications can be generated and escalated according to business needs, helping operational teams respond promptly to changes and incidents.

The dashboard capabilities are notable, providing over 600 customizable widgets for building interactive and visually rich dashboards. There is full support for live and historical data visualization, dynamic filtering, geospatial mapping, and advanced statistical overlays. These dashboards are usable both for internal users and for sharing data visualizations with customers or stakeholders, making them adaptable across many verticals such as industrial automation, environmental monitoring, and smart infrastructure.

The IoT platform was designed with extensibility and integration in mind. It supports multi-tenant operation out of the box—the same instance can be securely divided among many customers, each with isolated data and management capabilities. Developers and integrators can extend ThingsBoard with custom widgets, rule nodes or protocol adapters, while the rich REST and WebSocket APIs support integration with other IT and business systems. Whether deployed in the cloud or on-premises, the platform can be tailored for small POCs as well as for mission-critical

enterprise environments, and is available under the Apache License 2.0, giving organizations flexibility for commercial and private use.

The Blockchain architecture designed for the solution integrates a private blockchain platform with an ecosystem of modular and scalable services. The system ensures decentralization, security, and traceability of operations through a robust and interconnected infrastructure. Operations recorded on the private blockchain via through a dedicated service are notarized on a public blockchain, combining the performance, privacy, and access control of a private environment with the immutability, transparency, and distributed trust of a public network, thus strengthening data integrity and long-term verifiability.

Data Hubs like the Data Platform ensures an increasingly advanced information ecosystem, enabling the automation of data management, data analysis, and data usability and the implementation of analytics facilitating, simplifying and making the user experience more effective. It also promotes a data-driven approach to decision-making, geared towards sustainability, efficiency, and competitiveness.

1.2. Data ingestion tools

The Big Data Platform leverages flexible acquisition mechanisms to collect and manage heterogeneous data sets from multiple sources, such as:

- Files in various formats (CSV, JSON, XML, Avro)
- REST API
- External event-driven triggers

Within the Big Data Platform, Apache NiFi is the ingestion engine responsible for retrieving raw data from heterogeneous sources (IoT sensors, GIS systems, REST APIs, relational databases, and object storage) and efficiently channeling it into the Data Lake. Delivered as a containerized service on Kubernetes, NiFi benefits from horizontal scalability and high availability: each flow can be replicated across multiple pods, ensuring operational continuity and resilience in the event of load peaks. Thanks to its capabilities, NiFi is the heart of data orchestration, enabling both batch and streaming scenarios and ensuring a flexible, secure, and easily extensible infrastructure.

Hue serves as a centralized web interface for self-service exploration and management of data in the Data Lake. Deployed as a containerized service on Kubernetes, Hue offers key features, including

- a File Manager for browsing, uploading, and downloading files within Ozone storage
- an advanced SQL Editor for writing, running, and saving queries in Hive and Trino, with autocompletion, syntax highlighting, and the ability to save results as tables or CSV files
- the ability to create visualizations that combine SQL blocks and graphs

With these features, Hue enables users to explore data assets, accelerating the adoption of evidence-based insights while ensuring the security, traceability, and reusability of the resources created.

Apache Superset serves as the "DashBoard BI" module, providing a containerized web interface on Kubernetes for the self-service creation and use of reports, charts, and interactive dashboards. A drag-and-drop visualization editor allows the user to build charts and visualizations, selecting metrics and dimensions directly from the interface without writing code. Multiple visualizations can be assembled into custom layouts and organized into tabs to create dashboards. Its SQL Lab is an advanced environment for writing, executing, and saving SQL queries on engines such as Hive and Trino.

With Superset, analysts and stakeholders can independently explore large volumes of data, transform insights into actionable reports, and share results securely and traceably across the organization.

Apache Airflow acts as the central orchestrator of batch and real-time processes, coordinating the execution of complex data cleansing, transformation, and enrichment pipelines. Also delivered as a containerized service on Kubernetes, Airflow leverages the KubernetesExecutor to dynamically scale workers based on the workload, ensuring high availability and isolation of each task's dependencies. Each workflow is modeled as a DAG in Python, allowing programmatic definitions of dependencies, conditional branches, retry, and backfill. The internal scheduler activates DAGs according to custom calendars (cron, fixed intervals, end-of-month). Via the web UI, you can track the status of instances, view detailed logs, and restart individual tasks. It supports the automated deployment of new DAGs in CI/CD pipelines, on-demand triggers, and the retrieval of operational metadata for integration into other dashboards (e.g., Superset).

Airflow is a flexible and modular orchestrator capable of coordinating both traditional batch loads and near-real-time scenarios, ensuring timeliness, reproducibility, and end-to-end visibility of data engineering processes.

1.3. Data processing flow

NIR – Micro – Macro prototype

The NIR use case made it possible to automate and make less error-prone a series of operations that were previously performed manually by the operator.

NIR spectroscopy analysis output files in CSV format are processed specifically for each category (NIR, Micro, and Macro) using additional parameters and producing a table containing the results of the three experiments for all analyzed samples.

Each specific input file is uploaded by the user in a specific folder on the Ozone file system through Hue web UI. Those folders represent the input for a python script which performs the conversion of the data to be written to the output table. An Airflow DAG orchestrates and executes this script, which is located on the Ozone file system. The outcome of this process is in tabular format and can be queried to create analytics, visualization and dashboards, preliminarily on Hue and in Superset for more detailed and elaborated dashboards. For further details, please refer to the paragraph below "User evaluation".

Supply chain data blockchain solution

The traceability data related to the managed supply chains, which are generated by the Blockchain component, are acquired and saved in tabular format.

This use case represents the integration between the Supply Chain Traceability System (of the Blockchain component) and the Data Platform, through a REST API service exposed by the Traceability System itself. The data concerns all information from the managed supply chain, which is certified by the Traceability System as a result of the immutable notarization process.

The acquisition process occurs via a NiFi workflow, which allows data to be extracted from the REST service and written to the Platform (on the Ozone file system). The data is then organized in a structured table format for ease of use and visualization. Data can be queried to create analytics, visualization and dashboards, preliminarily on Hue and in Superset for more detailed and elaborated dashboards.

This use-case complements other data flowing into the platform, offering the possibility of performing analyses that integrate multiple data sources related to the territory.

Weather stations data

This activity involves the integration and configuration of Netsens sensors within the IoT platform designed for real-time acquisition and centralized monitoring of environmental data from distributed field stations. A custom connector automates polling of the Netsens API, handles authentication, and converts the acquired data for ingestion, enabling continuous collection of parameters such as temperature, humidity, rainfall, wind, and leaf wetness.

Gateway List > Connectors

Tempo reale - ultimo 15 minuti

Connectors

Enabled	Name ↑	Type	Configuration	Status	Actions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	netsens	CUSTOM	SYNC	●	🔍 ☰ 🗑️

CUSTOM Configuration v3.7.5

General Configuration*

```

1- {
2  "host": "https://api.netsens.it",
3  "authEndpoint": "/auth/token",
4  "username": "DUMMY",
5  "password": "DUMMY",
6  "tokenHeader": "Authorization",
7  "tokenPrefix": "Bearer ",
8  "endpoints": [
9  {
10   "url": "/data/list",
11   "method": "GET",
12   "stationIds": [
13     2386,
14     2387,
15     2391,
16     2389,
17     2392,
18     2394,
19     2395,
20     2396,
21     2406,
22     ...

```

Salva

The solution features interactive monitoring dashboards that provide geographic mapping of sensor locations and detailed real-time visualizations for each device. These dashboards display historical trends, current measurements, and key indicators using customizable charts and graphs, while also allowing the configuration of alert thresholds for automatic notifications on critical conditions.

Stazioni

Stazioni

Tempo reale - ultimo giorno

Nome ↑

- RL_01_Teglio
- RL_02_Quistello
- RL_03_Brescia
- RL_04_Sondrio
- RL_05_Torrazza Coste
- RL_06_Pozzologno
- RL_07_Paratico
- RL_08_Montecarlo Versiglia
- RL_09_San Colombano al Lambro

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The integration with Kafka ensures that every environmental data point collected from the Netsens sensors is instantly sent via Kafka to the Big Data Platform. This approach enables real-time data handling and guarantees efficient, low latency streaming of information without delays or backlogs

Metadata Geoportal

Updating the Big Data Platform with metadata relating to thematic maps managed on the ESRI geoportal. For this use case a NiFi workflow is responsible for the automated processing of input metadata files related to thematic maps, uploaded onto the Ozone file system. The outcome of this process is in tabular format and can be queried to create analytics, visualization and dashboards, preliminarily on Hue and in Superset for more detailed and elaborated dashboards.

This way it is possible to have an informative representation of the process and the Metadata of the thematic maps.

This case complements other data flowing into the platform, offering the possibility of performing analyses that integrate multiple data sources related to the territory.

metadati_portalgis
metadati_portalgis_log

Table 2a Metadata geoportal tables

module_title	citation_title	citation_edition	module_date	abstract	purpose	credit	representation_type	topic_category	keyword	filename
Limiti amministrativi	ISO 19115-3 Geographic Information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals	2014			NODES - Cartografia dei limiti amministrativi della Regione Lombardia	ERSAF	vector		ersaf; nodes; ersaf; nodes	Limiti_Ammministrativi-FS_metadata-19115.csv
Matrice Landrace	ISO 19115-3 Geographic Information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals	2014	2023-11-19T00:00:00	Identificazione delle aree di equilibrio tra genotipi eterogenei ed eterozigoti all'interno di una popolazione di una coltura che viene mantenuta mediante moltiplicazione continua in un dato insieme di condizioni climatiche del suolo e di allevamento	Identificazione delle aree di equilibrio tra genotipi eterogenei ed eterozigoti all'interno di una popolazione di una coltura che viene mantenuta mediante moltiplicazione continua in un dato insieme di condizioni climatiche del suolo e di allevamento	ERSAF	vector	biota; environment	Downloadable Data; ersaf; nodes; ersaf; nodes	Matrice_Landrace-FS_metadata-19115.csv
Stazioni meteo_temp	ISO 19115-3 Geographic Information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals	2014	2023-11-15T00:00:00	Stazioni meteo - rilevamento dati temperatura	temperatura °C	ERSAF	vector	climatology/MeteorologyAtmosphere; environment	Downloadable Data; ersaf; nodes; ersaf; nodes	Stazioni_meteo_temp-FS_metadata-19115.csv
Carta Pedologica	ISO 19115-3 Geographic Information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals	2014	2023-11-15T00:00:00	Carta delle caratteristiche e della distribuzione dei suoli	Carta delle caratteristiche e della distribuzione dei suoli	ERSAF	vector	environment	Downloadable Data; ERSAF; RICCAGIOIA; SPOKE; SPOKEB; ERSAF; RICCAGIOIA; SPOKE; SPOKEB; ERSAF; RICCAGIOIA; SPOKE; SPOKEB	Carta_Pedologica-FS_metadata-19115.csv
Mappe del vigore	ISO 19115-3 Geographic Information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals	2014			Mappatura del vigore dei vigneti da drone				RMS	Mappe_delVigore-FS_metadata-19115.csv
Zone DOC	ISO 19115-3 Geographic Information - Metadata - Part 1: Fundamentals	2014	2023-11-14T00:00:00	Area dei disciplinari per la produzione vitivinicola	Area dei disciplinari per la produzione vitivinicola	ERSAF	vector	environment	Downloadable Data; ERSAF; RICCAGIOIA; SPOKE; SPOKEB; ERSAF; RICCAGIOIA; SPOKE; SPOKEB; ERSAF; RICCAGIOIA; SPOKE; SPOKEB	Zone_DOC-FS_metadata-19115.csv

Table 3b Dashboard ERSAF – Metadata ESRI for use case Metadata Geoportal use case

1.4. Access

Access to the Big Data platform is reserved for authorized internal users.

Authentication is managed via a VPN connection and personal credentials to ensure controlled access to collaborative research projects. User profiling allows for differentiated access to data from the two databases created according to the two Spokes. Access to the user interface is managed via the platform's SSO mechanism (Keycloak/OpenLDAP), ensuring federated authentication and granular control of resource-level permissions.

1.5. User verification

A test of the platform has been conducted by the team of Prof. A. Gallo (Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore – Piacenza), who works on improving the efficiency of the agro-livestock system.

Introduction

The activity of NIR calibration for forages intended for zootechnical use represents a fundamental step in the quality and reliability of analyses. In order to build and keep predictive models updated, it is necessary to collect and integrate a large amount of samples and related information from different matrices. All this information concerning the quality and safety of feed must be aggregated into a single .xlsx file with a precise structure, which can be read by a script developed internally in R language.

This file constitutes the operational basis for each calibration and contains:

- the sample ID, to ensure correct traceability,
- 2224 wavelengths of the NIR spectrum,
- the chemical data obtained from laboratory analyses,
- the fermentative data, where applicable, obtained through GC-FID, appropriately transformed with several calculations to be expressed as %DM.

The screenshot shows a detailed Excel spreadsheet with the following structure:

- Columns 1-10:** Sample ID (ID) and various chemical data points (C1-C10).
- Columns 11-2224:** Wavelengths (W1-W2224) representing the NIR spectrum.
- Columns 2225-2300:** Additional chemical data points (C11-C20).
- Columns 2301-2400:** Fermentative data points (F1-F10).
- Columns 2401-2500:** Calculated values (V1-V10).

Overlaid on the spreadsheet is a legend box with the following items:

- ID SAMPLE
- NIR wavelengths
- Chemical data
- Fermentative data
- Values

Figure 1- Structure of the final dataset with all the information necessary for NIR calibration

The creation of the Excel matrix is a rather linear activity, but in practice it was a long, complex and entirely manual process, which requires extracting, adapting and standardizing very different data coming from heterogeneous instruments and formats. Each step depended on the precision of the operator, with consequent risks of information loss, duplication, or transcription errors.

Pre-platform activities

The preparation of this matrix required the extraction and integration of data from different tools, with heterogeneous formats. In particular:

- NIR Spectrum: the Bruker MPA II instrument produces an output file in .csv format with X/Y data orientation. Spectra are downloaded individually, so for each sample a separate file is generated. This made it necessary not only to readjust the orientation of the data into the correct format, but also to merge the multiple files into a single Excel file that had to be integrated with the other information. To achieve this, an

application was developed in R Studio which was not user-friendly for everyone, requiring at least minimal knowledge to correctly manage the procedure.

Figure 2 - Process of converting a .csv file using X/Y orientation into an .xlsx file using the R Studio application

- Chemical data: determined in the laboratory with different instrumental methods and collected separately, then transcribed into a single Excel file suitable for subsequent processing with spectral and fermentation data.

ID	5665	PH	SS	celulr	proteine	NDF	NDR	ADF	ADL	ND24	GRASS	AMIDO	ZUCCHERO	CA	P	MG	K	LACTIC	ACETIC	PH	TVFA	POOL	NDFPRO	ADFPRO
1	30.778812	3.71	95.355007	7.143802	7.7766359	42.289725	43.9897633	28.9950543	3.36475305	49.8886927	3.07380045	24.15426254	0.7518993	0.2649866	0.2881786	0.1829	1.7588737	5.87600085	5.1244822	3.7458985	10.798452	4.6109388	1.1432814	0.5258885
2	31.9979787	3.7	93.9863014	5.6804395	9.3788867	39.778872	40.6778988	25.1685446	2.8457183	52.6898901	2.8949338	28.9694262	1.0111442	0.3249268	0.2883363	0.2707954	1.4583886	5.1926253	4.8964442	3.9154577	9.3773861	5.4793479	1.4289391	0.8703781
3	36.7588189	3.87	95.1403961	5.2940174	8.81742095	35.6647641	37.3684975	23.9984541	2.7810455	45.7528864	1.6517115	33.5011022	0.8184298	0.2369772	0.2980256	0.1663905	1.581794	4.6812626	4.6207626	3.8541435	9.4076765	4.7596674	1.1112290	0.7864483
4	32.6988309	3.54	96.2915611	5.3066959	8.48598765	35.2974777	36.9974875	24.8312277	3.0571205	46.2469006	3.12763405	29.2073708	0.69395085	0.2291204	0.24782395	0.1665635	1.2167013	7.00583055	3.9090255	3.5384778	10.9433284	4.71526065	0.8223396	0.8021214
5	33.2527766	3.7	94.7677498	5.4005386	9.0250888	37.3732681	39.0732689	24.5960028	2.823956	44.6082745	2.9247715	31.3059983	1.0697554	0.2516281	0.2704565	0.1718683	1.5099384	4.90289	3.570781	3.8887761	8.2986265	4.5849924	1.3790624	0.9094403
6	30.6796831	3.8	95.4802009	6.2623933	8.4613007	42.8621521	44.5621561	28.7897835	3.2762225	50.9572734	3.0173588	24.4557007	1.0644668	0.2716786	0.3152132	0.1867955	1.5455874	4.9885778	3.8591077	9.8746462	4.9188629	1.2661921	0.8835853	
7	34.9517179	3.57	96.0482051	6.2036787	8.882171	38.5497734	40.0497729	25.5591304	3.10671733	51.7930761	2.9972497	28.3054898	1.0984455	0.2438781	0.30967217	0.17528047	1.5664479	5.03275107	4.23849697	3.86071157	9.607405	4.64733983	1.3584213	0.89487217
8	34.694927	3.7	95.6200752	5.3567584	7.8802141	36.9968071	38.696806	25.7452031	3.041782	48.2477417	2.9785819	32.395813	0.6927231	0.21679955	0.2643745	0.1668111	1.3681705	4.9416113	3.7307845	3.798149	8.601351	4.0132025	1.158641	0.8172505
9	34.4662579	3.84	97.7440291	5.14037395	8.06311225	38.8532639	40.532644	24.208306	2.7987895	51.3740902	2.9288415	34.6039582	0.7382661	0.2088125	0.2754532	0.1446435	1.1835305	4.1569392	3.9737827	3.85837215	8.4070482	1.0285355	0.7968215	
10	30.8767185	3.89	98.314236	5.2875738	7.8424257	39.330242	41.0302392	25.3096547	2.8456509	53.2017956	3.0048036	32.0434908	0.7682361	0.20989135	0.2905579	0.1466043	1.9027356	4.8789375	3.8602616	7.95987005	9.2074397	4.8373725	0.9026261	0.8115445
11	33.7734617	4.01	98.6869164	5.92876225	7.80256365	41.3292275	43.0292339	25.9429198	3.0536307	53.2138558	2.9099225	30.413724	0.9367601	0.2287416	0.2830936	0.13325115	1.302884	4.1527462	3.125394	3.8551258	7.76444245	4.0243765	1.3118855	0.908611
12	35.1821018	3.97	98.4815521	5.9924715	8.0675075	38.2885113	39.9885178	25.1262392	2.97257455	53.8567829	2.94952715	33.326767	0.8444615	0.2164831	0.2920971	0.13770865	1.4258723	4.1449668	3.16165165	3.8715172	8.0888791	4.2887729	1.09829545	0.8701129
13	30.8545482	3.59	98.9766555	5.75257335	10.4653825	39.8019068	41.0210024	24.9614544	3.1748795	51.4464639	3.00338615	25.5212138	1.0111765	0.2467005	0.31648925	0.14973215	1.6437906	4.1393845	3.75394215	10.4008497	5.7886231	1.4541475	0.9554802	
14	35.06537	3.69	97.9296418	5.2542522	8.0328705	36.3120583	38.021333	22.6975432	2.7837975	52.1593262	2.7046515	34.8883113	1.2227785	0.1908925	0.304392	0.1429646	1.3671012	5.6626101	2.5885975	3.7423315	8.4599107	4.4207666	0.914761	0.7924535
15	31.1690434	3.82	97.9061882	5.4319485	7.8722062	39.9435082	41.643509	25.9457398	2.9986987	53.2479911	2.9785819	30.326889	0.9818075	0.21384005	0.2852441	0.1449847	1.3541339	4.7594252	3.8342085	3.9512744	8.5620146	4.2504205	1.0444123	0.8394075
16	33.5042625	3.81	97.0748406	5.41794375	5.64500265	39.1280736	40.8268839	26.474453	3.54648335	51.9911919	3.1192739	31.703219	0.7080242	0.2016885	0.3167884	0.1355338	1.4152123	4.3632808	4.88972575	3.8495204	10.0313741	4.8802049	1.8971787	0.84545795
17	35.2936026	3.81	97.9750706	5.4589187	7.335011	49.2817488	40.941777	31.7639399	3.5605555	54.363399	3.914885	34.740413	0.9426469	0.20398485	0.3204212	0.1322165	1.45711495	3.8112545	4.6478804	3.8857689	9.1196542	4.078375	1.3331923	1.051255
18	34.412065	3.85	97.5291329	5.6043768	7.5841267	44.372366	47.342366	27.545516	3.17280305	55.7004065	2.9394896	28.620356	1.1145385	0.2303956	0.3077862	0.14905775	1.4238565	4.3937965	3.7560915	3.822488	8.9835493	4.4314003	1.123265	0.9712426
19	37.715172	3.97	97.7502251	5.239887	7.25683095	40.9716985	42.4819635	26.3568163	2.9921121	53.112484	2.9775555	34.0007496	0.8012525	0.2036622	0.3016843	0.1323955	1.3718618	4.0344602	4.308742	3.864598	9.11071255	4.5470779	0.9977254	0.8707625
20	31.5368609	3.75	97.709616	5.3271955	7.4945705	40.3814402	42.0841513	26.677471	3.0000016	54.1871519	2.809349	31.643469	0.9614925	0.1913225	0.2803337	0.12299375	1.33021155	5.0095835	3.7687478	3.74311575	9.3108785	4.4055975	0.8895765	0.8282665
21	30.9450233	3.93	94.9536537	5.7982211	7.8757736	36.2957777	38.1575785	23.249584	3.6485583	45.2275177	2.9813648	34.5262651	0.8794248	0.2993753	0.3066252	0.1795805	1.1446912	3.3800212	3.9453885	1.8516703	5.1197538	2.5380055	0.4772704	0.3403083
22	36.0489794	3.49	93.5081062	5.1379638	8.1011043	39.9327144	35.6327056	22.33482	2.274905	51.0479469	2.9942349	36.4084644	0.8025218	0.2201539	0.2753506	0.1252721	1.3057107	6.3240402	3.47625	3.7959988	10.0591469	5.4483918	1.0173701	0.6082843
23	34.7975217	3.55	93.7480509	5.4831882	8.0985527	37.4064121	39.1064129	24.4367495	2.5955152	52.905481	2.9989058	32.9099295	0.91314	0.2447954	0.248414	0.1617691	1.9995949	5.8689866	3.522006	3.761014	9.4455001	4.9464741	1.2409896	0.7611075
24	33.284038	3.57	93.8273774	5.3386162	8.3779683	40.208754	41.9058268	25.40729	2.8213948	50.3558087	2.839	31.1468665	0.8841474	0.2491969	0.2959996	0.1470772	1.315907	5.4483035	3.9626967	3.8345513	8.947742	1.3506307	0.8202424	
25	36.053282	3.8	94.2392364	5.719455	7.9516731	37.7995873	39.4995861	24.872123	2.6122748	50.7370504	2.9492443	30.0197906	0.9804946	0.2552586	0.2819867	0.172653	1.372318	3.8557589	3.8408364	3.9718901	7.9842317	4.717347	1.2248571	0.7383274
26	36.053282	3.8	94.2392364	5.719455	7.9516731	37.7995873	39.4995861	24.872123	2.6122748	50.7370504	2.9492443	30.0197906	0.9804946	0.2552586	0.2819867	0.172653	1.372318	3.8557589	3.8408364	3.9718901	7.9842317	4.717347	1.2248571	0.7383274
27	30.930282	3.8	94.2392364	5.719455	7.9516731	37.7995873	39.4995861	24.872123	2.6122748	50.7370504	2.9492443	30.0197906	0.9804946	0.2552586	0.2819867	0.172653	1.372318	3.8557589	3.8408364	3.9718901	7.9842317	4.717347	1.2248571	0.7383274
28	30.1239482	3.42	94.2903671	5.5192449	7.8851091	40.6330206	42.1633072	27.4218874	2.9342423	51.1508824	2.8560996	29.6474686	0.8397281	0.2361916	0.2673982	0.1431401	1.4461817	5.8557044	3.9655198	3.7526111	10.134624	4.7445132	1.0299937	0.8014213
29	33.5844189	3.5	93.9150883	5.0353684	7.9797934	35.5337408	37.0237408	23.8072921	2.8162048	51.1770088	2.8162048	34.560196	0.9804946	0.1991558	0.2986889	0.1416722	1.2636872	5.222641	3.3004964	3.8006023	4.5536782	4.5536782	0.6707335	
30	33.773132	3.81	93.5562395	4.960975	8.1835609	39.273859	40.9738541	26.2565813	2.7516456	50.8285217	3.1445445	29.074646	0.8804928	0.2501648	0.2660114	0.1585052	1.303817	6.1594488	3.6013174	3.6955508	10.6232619	5.9065952	1.219544	0.7505533
31	34.4905863	3.66	94.4100914	5.067828	8.1818325	40.5183258	42.5194837	24.5194837	2.8400194	51.4740717	2.9154428	31.5432482	1.047928	0.2681869	0.2668812	0.1420261	1.2340541	5.7764898	3.9674927	3.799469	6.0697074	1.098854</		

- Fermentation data: extracted from the GC-FID, they required transformations and preliminary calculations in order to be expressed as %DM. Once the calculations were completed, only the final values were reported in the Excel file, manually transposed so that they could be standardized and integrated with the spectral and chemical data. The entire operation of selection, transposition, and insertion of useful data was therefore carried out manually.

The image shows a detailed view of an Excel spreadsheet. The columns are labeled with letters from A to AP, and the rows are numbered from 1 to 77. The data is organized into several sections, with a prominent yellow box highlighting a specific area. A red arrow points to a cell within this highlighted area. A watermark reading 'ID SAMPLE Fermentative data' is overlaid on the spreadsheet. The data appears to be a matrix of numerical values, likely representing fermentation parameters for different samples.

Figure 4 - Process for calculating fermentation data from the .xlsx file

Critical aspects of the process

This approach, in order to obtain a single file containing spectral, chemical, and fermentation data for each sample, although functional, presented numerous limitations:

- High operational complexity: the integration of heterogeneous data required time and attention, with long and complex procedures.
- Repetitiveness of steps: much of the work was based on copy-and-paste operations, which, in addition to being time-consuming, did not add value.
- High risk of error: the multiplicity of manual steps made it easy to lose information, enter incorrect values or confuse samples, resulting in poor traceability because, in case of data inconsistencies, it was difficult to quickly trace the origin of the error.

Data platform

HUE

It has a sufficiently intuitive interface. The layout and design are simple and immediately draw the user's attention to the functionality menu.

The platform access interface is basic and straightforward. Access requests, troubleshooting and alternative access features are all offered in a single, simplified interactive panel.

Figure 5 - Login page

Among its various features, HUE allows you to upload source files directly to the platform's file system. In our case, these source files correspond to the chemical, fermentation, and spectral data. This is the first step in entering raw data into the system.

Figure 6 - File upload system

Thanks to the traceability of file positioning, it is easy to navigate through the various file directories and immediately view their contents.

A similar structure is associated with the data display interface of the general database—OZONE—which allows you to navigate smoothly through any file or database present. This is the “place” where files are uploaded and where the outputs of the processes reside. The folder structure suggests an organised workflow for data ingestion and processing.

Figure 7 - Organized folders containing raw and merged files

The available data is displayed using the KYUBII platform, an intuitive SQL Editor that allows extensive navigation of data in structured formats, querying to interrogate, select and filter the data contained in each table. Finally, it is possible to view the query results in table format.

Figure 8 - Final table with all necessary information

In addition, Kyubii features an integrated platform of basic visualisation tools that allow you to create bar charts and line graphs directly from SQL query results.

Figure 9 - Bar and line graphs for each upload sample

In bar graphs, you can plot the value of one or more wavelengths (Y-AXIS, e.g. 12488) for each sample (X-AXIS, e.g. ID). This is useful for quick comparisons between samples at specific wavelengths.

In line graphs, you can attempt to visualise a spectrum by selecting one wavelength for the X-axis and one for the Y-axis, grouping by ID. However, as can be seen from the image (HUE- SQL Dashboard 2.png), the result is not a typical spectral graph (Absorbance vs. Wavelength), confirming the limitations of this feature, which is not suitable for visualising complex spectral data.

AIRFLOW

Platform for orchestrating and automating data processing pipelines. In this case, it is used to execute complex scripts in a controlled and repeatable manner that clean, format, transform and merge raw spectral and analytical data, generating final databases ready for the calibration, formed by sample ID and all the necessary information.

The control dashboard shows the list of DAGs, i.e. the automatic cycles (pipelines) we use to read, manipulate and produce final data that is combined and useful for analysis. It provides an immediate overview of the status of each pipeline: success (green circles), failure (red circles), running, etc. This is essential for checking that the automatic processes are running smoothly.

From this interface, it is possible to manually start a process ("trigger"), pause it or view its detailed logs.

Figure 10 – Visualization of automatic pipelines

Once all the raw files that will constitute the final .xlsx file have been uploaded to the HUE platform, all you need to do is start the process.

At the end of each process, the processed files are saved in a specific directory within HUE.

SUPERSET

Apache Superset is positioned as the final, interactive layer of the entire data architecture. Its purpose is to connect to the databases processed and made available by HUE and Airflow, transforming tabular data into a visual analysis environment. It connects directly to the final databases and transforms them into interactive, informative dashboards, allowing trends to be identified and individual silage samples to be analysed in detail.

Figure 11- Navigation interface for mathematical data metrics

The dashboard is logically organised with thematic tabs: Summary of samples included at the time of database merging, chemical data, fermentative data and NIR spectra are some of the key points on which you can focus your attention. This allows for clear navigation and analysis focused on specific aspects of the data.

The summary tab uses large numerical displays to show the average values of important parameters (e.g. ethanol, acetone) at a glance, providing an immediate summary. On the left, the

interactive filter based on sample ID allows you to select specific samples and dynamically update the entire dashboard to display only the relevant data.

Figure 12 - Different types of graphic visualization of chemical and fermentative parameters

For chemical and fermentative data, Superset combines a detailed table (for consulting precise values) with a bar chart (histogram). This dual display satisfies both the need for numerical precision and that of immediate visual comparison between samples. The bar charts are configured to compare different parameters (e.g. pH, protein, NDF for chemicals) for each sample, providing an effective comparative overview.

Figure 13 – NIR spectra graphics

Superset correctly uses line graphs to plot NIR spectra, representing absorbance as a function of wavelength. Each coloured line corresponds to a different sample. The most important feature for spectral analysis is the control panel below the graph. This tool allows the user to select a specific region of the spectrum and zoom in on it, an essential function for examining peaks and spectral features in detail. You can click on the sample IDs in the legend to hide or show individual spectra, facilitating comparison between subsets of samples.

The Superset Visualisation platform provides a Business Intelligence (BI) interface and visual analytics for exploring the final processed data, transforming complex data tables into interactive dashboards that allow end users, even those without technical expertise, to analyse spectral and analytical data from silage.

Conclusion

With the integration of the data platform, the entire workflow that was previously carried out manually has now been fully automated. Today, our only task is to upload the raw input files of chemical, fermentative, and spectral data, directly into the system. From there, the automated pipelines manage all subsequent steps: cleaning, transforming, merging, and storing the data in structured databases ready for calibration.

In addition, thanks to the integrated visualisation tools, we now have rapid and intuitive access to processed information. The system allows us not only to navigate the data efficiently but also to explore it through interactive dashboards and graphical representations, making the analysis of chemical parameters, fermentative results, and NIR spectra both faster and more effective.

B) Prediction models

2.1 NIR models and hierarchical approach

Near-Infrared (NIR) spectroscopy combined with machine learning provides rapid, non-destructive analysis of silage composition. This study developed comprehensive predictive models by treating micro and macro components as separate analytical targets, recognizing their distinct biochemical characteristics and importance in silage quality assessment. The dataset comprised NIR spectral measurements from 2,224 wavelengths (independent variables) paired with their corresponding chemical compositions (dependent variables) for various silage compounds. The analytical approach distinguishes between MICRO components (fermentation byproducts including alcohols and organic acids) and MACRO components (structural constituents and nutrients), as these categories exhibit different spectral responses and require tailored modeling strategies. Figure 1 shows the complete methodology workflow from data acquisition through model validation.

Figure 1. Proposed methodology for NIR silage prediction.

Methodology:

The analytical framework was designed to handle the complexity of silage composition by developing specialized models for two distinct component categories:

- MICRO Components Analysis:** Fermentation byproducts were analyzed both as continuous variables (regression) and categorical variables (classification). The regression approach predicted exact concentrations while classification determined presence/absence or concentration levels. This dual approach was necessary because certain volatile compounds show non-linear responses in NIR spectra, making categorical assessment more reliable for quality control purposes.
- MACRO Components Analysis:** Structural and nutritional components were modeled through regression due to their continuous nature and stronger correlation with NIR spectra. These components, being primary constituents of the feed matrix, show more direct spectral responses.

Data preprocessing included standardization (z-score normalization) and systematic PCA optimization (1-100 components) tailored for each target variable. Five regression algorithms were evaluated: Linear Regression, Random Forest, Support Vector Regressor, K-Nearest Neighbors, and XGBoost. The dataset was split 80/20 for training-validation/test with 5-fold cross-validation for robust performance assessment.

Results - MICRO Components:

Regression Models (concentration prediction):

- Ethanol: XGBoost (82 PCA) achieved $R^2 = 0.798$ (validation), 36.5% test
- Methanol: Random Forest (58 PCA) achieved $R^2 = 0.649$ (validation), 74.1% test
- Lactic acid: XGBoost (20 PCA) achieved $R^2 = 0.498$ (validation), 0.19% test
- Total alcohols: Linear Regression (52 PCA) achieved $R^2 = 0.476$ (validation), 16.5% test

Classification Models (qualitative assessment):

Multi-class classification (absent/low/high levels)

- Isobutyric acid: XGBoost (90 PCA) - 86.8% (validation), 73.5% test
- Isovaleric acid: Logistic Regression (41 PCA) - 90.6% (validation), 69.8% test
- Ethyl lactate: XGBoost (73 PCA) - 69.8% (validation), 79.2% test

Binary classification models:

2-phenyl ethanol: Random Forest (11 PCA) - 84.9% validation, 75.5% test

Acetaldehyde: Random Forest (13 PCA) - 84.9% validation, 79.2% test

Results - MACRO Components (all regression):

- Proteins: Linear Regression (73 PCA) - $R^2 = 0.868$ validation, 0.955 test
- (AMIDO): Linear Regression (73 PCA) - $R^2 = 0.971$ validation, 0.952 test
- (ZUCCHERI): Linear Regression (96 PCA) - $R^2 = 0.953$ validation, 0.888 test
- NDF: Linear Regression (90 PCA) - $R^2 = 0.793$ validation, 0.807 test
- ADF: Linear Regression (68 PCA) - $R^2 = 0.793$ validation, 0.861 test
- ADL: Linear Regression (68 PCA) - $R^2 = 0.803$ validation, 0.906 test
- (GRASSI): Linear Regression (80 PCA) - $R^2 = 0.821$ validation, 0.633 test
- (ceneri): Linear Regression (97 PCA) - $R^2 = 0.756$ validation, 0.743 test
- Minerals (Ca, P, Mg, K): Linear Regression achieved $R^2 > 0.75$ for most minerals

In order to further improve the model performance, hierarchical approach is also implemented. This approach enhances prediction accuracy by leveraging biochemical relationships between macro and micro components. This methodology uses macro component predictions as additional features for micro component modeling. The two-stage process recognizes that fermentation products (micro) are influenced by substrate composition (macro). Stage 1 predicts macro components from NIR spectra using optimized PCA and best-performing algorithms. Stage 2 combines these macro predictions with original spectral data to create an enriched feature set for micro component prediction.

The proposed ML approach for prediction of nutrient content demonstrated strong prediction capabilities for micro and macro nutrients.

2.2 Biogas models

Machine learning-based prediction of energy and biogas quality in full-scale biogas plants represents a critical advancement for optimizing anaerobic digestion processes. Biogas production depends significantly on microbial metabolism, influenced by reactor conditions like temperature and pH, further complicating predictive modeling. Traditional modeling methods often fail to adequately account for these complex, nonlinear interactions, necessitating advanced analytical techniques.

Figure 2. Dataset for energy and biogas quality in full-scale biogas plant.

The study developed machine learning models to predict biogas production parameters in full-scale anaerobic digestion processes utilizing operational data from reactors R1 and R2. Input variables were categorized into two cases:

- Case 1 included inoculum properties, Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (NIR) measurements, operational parameters (temperature, pH, Volatile Fatty Acids), and microbial community composition as inputs.
- Case 2 treated microbial communities as predicted outputs alongside energy and methane production. The dataset comprised 205 features from 40 samples, including climatic factors, feed characteristics (daily slurry input, total solids, volatile solids), and biochemical indicators.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was employed to handle the high-dimensional dataset, reducing multicollinearity and computational complexity while retaining critical information. Five supervised regression algorithms were tested: Linear Regression, Random Forest, Support

Vector Regressor (SVR), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and XGBoost. The dataset was partitioned into training (80%), validation (10%), and testing (10%) subsets.

PCA preprocessing systematically enhanced predictive accuracy compared to raw data processing. For methane and carbon dioxide, SVR with PCA achieved 96.4% R^2 on validation sets, representing a 5.65% improvement over non-PCA models. Energy yield prediction reached exceptional accuracy with Random Forest (99.8% validation R^2 , 97.1% test R^2).

In Case 2 analysis, microbial compositions were treated as target variables, demonstrating the models' capability to predict individual microbial abundances with high accuracy. Key taxa including g__Proteiniphilum_R2 ($R^2 = 0.976$ test), g__Clostridium_sensu_stricto_1_R1 ($R^2 = 0.982$ test), and f__Anaerolineaceae_R1 ($R^2 = 0.917$ test) were predicted with strong R^2 scores. Overall, PCA-based models showed better generalization and avoided overfitting compared to non-PCA models.

Figure 3. Performance analysis of case 1 with PCA and no PCA

Figure 4. Performance analysis of case 2 with PCA and no PCA

This work provides biogas plant operators with predictive tools capable of forecasting energy production and gas quality based on readily available process parameters.

C) Satellite data

In this chapter, the applications realized using satellite data in the framework of the project are reported below.

3.1 Yield prediction

There is a significant research gap on the individual influence of the vegetation features on crop yield. Hence, experiments were conducted to study the influence of vegetation features on the yield of corn, wheat, and soybeans. One openly accessible ground reference dataset at the Kellogg Biological Station, Hickory Corners, MI, USA, on a set of local farmland fields (42.420°N - 42.391°N, 85.366°W - 85.404°W) during 1996 - 2013 is used here as the ground truth, with Landsat as the spaceborne source of data. It has been observed that vegetation indices which are sensitive to chlorophyll content are most influential for the yield prediction of corn. A conference paper based on the proposed technique and findings has been presented at the InGARSS 2024 conference.

Figure 5: importance of features for yield prediction.

Figure 6: performance analysis of yield prediction algorithm.

3.2 Manuring detection

In this work, manures are identified using time series multispectral and radar satellite data over Spain and Italy. The proposed work uses feature importance techniques to identify the top five multispectral and radar features that have a higher correlation to manure. It has different machine learning algorithms which provide moderate accuracies on the separation of manure and non-manure. The experimentation concluded that combining Sentinel-2 optical and Landsat-8 thermal indexes allows achieving the best classification performances and the spectral signature of manure application is homogeneous within fields located in the same country. The work is one of the introductory studies in manure detection which can be further helpful in environmental regulations, promotion of responsible farming practices, and safeguarding ecosystems

Figure 7: Conceptual flowchart for manuring detection

Figure 8: samples from Ground Truth data.

Figure 9: performance analysis.

3.3 Drought detection

We considered different areas of India such as Amaravati, Rajasthan, and others for drought detection. Different indices including vegetation features are employed over Sentinel-2 images. For ground truth, we are considering different news articles and India's official drought monitoring website. It provides an accuracy of 89% in XGBoost. We have further used an internal majority voting to find a district with drought. This provides ~100% accuracy to detect draughts. We have communicated a scientific report on the findings in MDPI.

Figure 10: conceptual workflow of satellite-based drought detection.

Figure 11: drought declaration procedure.

Figure 12: Machine learning workflow

Figure 13: performance analysis. Top features by importance.

Figure 14: performance analysis. Comparison of ROC curves for all models.

3.4 Rice paddy field detection

Accurate rice area monitoring is critical for food security and agricultural policy in smallholder farming regions, yet conventional remote sensing approaches struggle with the spatiotemporal heterogeneity characteristic of fragmented agricultural landscapes. This study developed a phenology-driven classification framework that systematically adapts to local agro-ecological variations across 32 districts in Telangana, India during the 2018-19 Rabi rice season. The research reveals significant spatiotemporal diversity, with phenological timing varying by up to 50 days between districts and field sizes ranging from 0.01 to 2.94 hectares. Our district-specific calibration approach achieved 93.3% overall accuracy, with strong validation against official government statistics ($R^2 = 0.920$) demonstrating excellent agreement between remotely sensed and ground truth data. The framework successfully mapped 732,345 hectares by adapting to agro-climatic variations, with Northern districts requiring extended land preparation phases (up to 55 days) while Southern districts showed compressed cultivation cycles. Field size analysis revealed accuracy declining 6.8 percentage points from medium to tiny fields, providing insights for operational monitoring in fragmented landscapes. These findings demonstrate that remote sensing frameworks must embrace rather than simplify landscape complexity, advancing region-specific agricultural monitoring approaches that maintain scientific rigor while serving practical policy and food security applications.

Figure 15: methodological framework of satellite-based drought detection

Figure 16: comparison of phenological cycles in the analysed districts.

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